

thiourea (0.1 mole) and ethanol (55 ml) was refluxed for 1.5 hr. 4-(4'-Acetamido-phenyl)-2-(substituted amino)-thiazoles were isolated following the method of Hantzsh¹. These compounds were refluxed with 2 N NaOH (14 ml) and ethanol for 45 min. Ethanol was distilled off and the reaction mixture poured in water. The solid product was filtered, washed and crystallised from ethanol. The melting points and analysis are given in Table 1.

General procedure for the synthesis of 4-[4'-(p-substituted benzene sulphonamido)-phenyl]-2-(substituted amino)-thiazoles (II): A mixture of 4-(4'-amino-phenyl)-2-(substituted amino)-thiazole (0.01 mole), p-substituted benzene sulphonyl chloride (0.01 mole) and dry pyridine (20 ml) was heated on water bath for 1.0 hr and then kept at room temp for 36 hr. The reaction mixture was poured in ice containing little conc H₂SO₄ with constant stirring. The crude product washed with dil NaHCO₃ soln and distilled water, was crystallised from ethanol.

p-Methyl- and p-acetamido benzene sulphonyl chloride were condensed with different 4-(4'-amino-phenyl)-2-(substituted amino)-thiazoles. The 4-(4'-N-acetamido sulphonamido)-2-(substituted amino)-thiazole derivatives were hydrolysed with 2 N NaOH to 4-(4'-sulphanilamido)-2-(substituted amino)-thiazoles and crystallised from ethanol. The melting points and analysis are given in Table 1.

Activity: Some representative compounds from each series were tested against four different organisms viz., *V. comma*, *M. tuberculosis*, *S. typhi* and *S. aureus*. None of them was found to be active.

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Selective Methylation of Quercetin and Myricetin

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SEVERAL methods are known for selective methylation of flavonoids¹⁻³. The key factor permitting methylation of certain hydroxyl groups in preference to others is the differential acidity of the hydroxyl groups placed at different positions of the flavone nucleus. The pioneering work in this

direction was done by Simpson and Beton¹ who studied the methylation of flavones and flavonols with dimethyl sulphate in refluxing acetone in presence of sodium bicarbonate and postulated the acidity order of the flavone hydroxyls as 7 > 4' > 3' > 3 on the basis of the results. But recent spectroscopic data, particularly the observation⁴ that flavones bearing a hydroxyl group at 3 rather than 3' position exhibit bathochromic shift in uv spectra in presence of a weak base like sodium acetate, clearly indicate the enhanced acidity of the hydroxyl group at 3 position compared to that at 3' position. This is clearly reflected in our selective methylation experiments with polyhydroxyflavones like myricetin (1, R=R₁=R₂=H) and quercetin (2, R=R₁=R₂=H) which gave in our hands 3,7,4'-trimethyl ethers (1 and 2, R=R₂=H, R₁=Me) as major products and 3,7,3',4'-tetramethyl ethers (1 and 2, R=H, R₁=R₂=Me) as the minor constituents. It was further observed that replacement of sodium bicarbonate with anhydrous sodium acetate gave essentially 7,4'-dimethyl ethers and the major product of methylation of quercetin with dimethyl sulphate in presence of sodium acetate was 7,4'-dimethylquercetin (3). The partially methylated flavonols were fully characterised from detailed spectral analysis of the compounds, their derivatives and also by degradative studies in some cases. Thus, the major compound obtained from myricetin yielded a triethylether (1, R₁=Me, R=R₂=Et)

which on alkali hydrolysis afforded ω,4-dimethoxy-2-ethoxy-6-hydroxy-acetophenone (4) and 3,5-diethyl-4-methyl gallic acid. Similarly, ethylation and subsequent alkali hydrolysis of the major product obtained from quercetin furnished the acetophenone, 4 and O-ethyl-isovanillic acid.

Experimental

Melting points were taken on a Toshniwal apparatus and are uncorrected. UV spectra were recorded on a Cary-14 instrument using spectrograde methanol (E.M.). IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 720 spectrophotometer in Nujol mull. ¹H NMR spectra were taken on Bruker WH-90 and Varian A-60D instruments using deuteriochloroform as solvent and TMS as internal standard. Anhydrous Na₂SO₄ was normally used

for drying organic solvents. Analytical samples were routinely dried over P_2O_5 for 24 hr *in vacuo*. Silica gel for column chromatography refers to B.D.H. (60-120 mesh).

Methylation of myricetin to 3,7,4'-trimethylmyricetin (1, $R=R_2=H$, $R_1=Me$) and 3,7,3',4'-tetramethylmyricetin (1, $R=H$, $R_1=R_2=Me$): A mixture of myricetin (4 g), freshly distilled Me_2SO_4 (5 ml) and $NaHCO_3$ (25 g) was refluxed under anhydrous condition with dry Me_2CO (500 ml) for 12 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled, filtered and the filtrate was concentrated and chromatographed over a bed of silica gel (100 g). The column after initial washing with C_6H_6 to remove unreacted Me_2SO_4 was first eluted with C_6H_6 - Me_2CO (49:1) mixture to afford 3,7,3',4'-tetramethylmyricetin (0.8 g) and then with C_6H_6 - Me_2CO (19:1) to furnish 3,7,4'-trimethylmyricetin (2.5 g).

3,7,4'-Trimethylmyricetin crystallised from MeOH as fine yellow needles, m.p. 207-08° (Lit.⁵ m.p. 208-10°), $C_{18}H_{16}O_8$, λ_{max} (MeOH) 262, 346 nm ($\log \epsilon$, 4.41, 4.36). MS: m/e 360 (M^+), 346, 345, 332, 331, 317, 167. Found: C, 59.78; H, 4.64. $C_{18}H_{16}O_8$ requires C, 60.00; H, 4.48%. Colourless crystals of triacetate, $C_{24}H_{20}O_{11}$, m.p. 196-97°; 1H nmr: δ 2.35 and 2.45 (6H and 3H *s* each, 3-OAc), 3.84 and 3.89 (6H and 3H *s* each, 3-OMe), 6.60 and 6.80 (1H *d* each, $J=2.5$ Hz, C-6 and C-8 H), 7.72 (2H, *s*, C-2' and C-6'-H). Found: C, 59.98; H, 4.72. $C_{24}H_{20}O_{11}$ requires C, 59.26; H, 4.56%. Triethylether $C_{24}H_{20}O_8$, m.p. 139°. Found: C, 64.34; H, 6.18. $C_{24}H_{20}O_8$ requires C, 64.85; H, 6.35%.

Alkali hydrolysis of 3,7,4'-trimethyl 5,3',5'-triethyl myricetin to ω ,4-dimethoxy-2-ethoxy-6-hydroxy acetophenone (4) and 3,5-diethyl-4-methyl gallic acid: A solution of 3,7,4'-trimethyl-5,3',5'-triethyl myricetin (0.5 g) in ethanolic NaOH (3 N; 70 ml) was refluxed on water bath for 1 hr. The solvent from the reaction mixture was removed by evaporation, the residue diluted with water, acidified with dil. H_2SO_4 (6 N) and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed several times with aq. $NaHCO_3$ and then with water, dried and evaporated to give a phenolic solid (0.09 g) which crystallised from methanol as colourless needles of 4, $C_{12}H_{16}O_8$, (M^+ , 240), m.p. 95°; 1H nmr: δ 3.55 and 3.85 (3H, *s* each, R-OMe and Ar-OMe), 1.5 (3H, *t*, $-OCH_2CH_3$), 1.45 (2H, *q*, $-OCH_2CH_3$), 5.92 and 6.12 (1H, *d* each, $J=2.5$ Hz, C-3 and C-5 H), 4.7 (2H, *s*, $-COCH_2OCH_3$), 13.85 (1H, *br*, chelated ArOH); MS: m/e 240 (M^+), 195 (M^+-CH_2OMe), 167 (M^+-COCH_2OMe). Found: C, 59.72; H, 6.85. $C_{12}H_{16}O_8$ requires C, 59.99; H, 6.71%.

The combined bicarbonate washings of the above ether extract was acidified and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed, dried and evaporated to dryness to give a solid (0.12 g) which crystallised from petrol (60-80°) as needles of 3,5-diethyl-4-methyl gallic acid, m.p. 108°; 1H nmr: δ 3.90 (3H, *s*, -OMe), 1.40 (6H, *t*, $J=7$ Hz) and 4.20 (4H, *q*, $J=7$ Hz, 2-OEt), 7.40 (2H, *s*, C-2 and C-6 H), 10.6

(1H, *br*, CO_2H), identical with synthetic sample¹⁰ of 3,5-diethyl-4-methyl gallic acid (m.m.p., ir).

3,7,3',4'-Tetramethylmyricetin crystallised from MeOH as pale yellow needles, $C_{19}H_{18}O_8$, m.p. 148-50° (Lit.⁷ m.p. 149-51°). Found: C, 60.73; H, 4.74. $C_{19}H_{18}O_8$ requires C, 60.96; H, 4.85%. It gave a diacetate, m.p. 185-86°; 1H nmr: δ 2.35 and 2.45 (3H, *s* each, 2-OAc), 3.82, 3.90, 3.95 and 3.96 (3H, *s* each, 4-OMe), 6.58 and 6.78 (1H, *d* each, $J=2.5$ Hz, C-6 and C-8 H), 7.38 and 7.60 (1H, *d* each, $J=2.5$ Hz, C-2' and C-6'-H); MS: m/e 374 (M^+) 360, 359, 331, 167.

Selective methylation of quercetin to 3,7,4'-trimethylquercetin (2, $R=R_2=H$, $R_1=Me$) and 3,7,3',4'-tetramethylquercetin (2, $R=H$, $R_1=R_2=Me$): Methylation of quercetin (2 g) with Me_2SO_4 in presence of $NaHCO_3$ and subsequent chromatography of the reaction mixture furnished trimethylquercetin (0.96 g) and tetramethylquercetin (0.36 g).

3,7,4'-Trimethylquercetin crystallised from MeOH as yellow microneedles, $C_{18}H_{16}O_7$, m.p. 174° (Lit.⁸ m.p. 172-73°). Found: C, 62.58; H, 4.90. $C_{18}H_{16}O_7$ requires C, 62.79; H, 4.68%. It gave a diacetate, m.p. 173-75°; 1H nmr (90 MHz): δ 2.35 and 2.45 (3H, *s* each, 2-OAc), 3.80, 3.89, 3.91 and 2.45 (3H, *s* each, 3-OMe), 6.61 and 6.83 (1H, *d* each, $J=2$ Hz, C-6 and C-8 H), 7.08 (1H, *d*, $J=9$ Hz, C-5' H), 7.81 (1H, *d*, $J=2$ Hz, C-2' H), 8.05 (1H, *dd*, $J_1=9$ Hz, $J_2=2$ Hz, C-6' H). Found: C, 61.54; H, 4.95. $C_{20}H_{20}O_9$ requires C, 61.68; H, 4.71%. MS: m/e 344 (M^+), 330, 329, 315, 301, 287.

Ethylation of 3,7,4'-trimethylquercetin followed by alkali hydrolysis *in situ* gave the acetophenone (4) and O-ethylisovanillic acid, m.p. 164° (Lit.⁹ m.p. 165-66°).

3,7,3',4'-Tetramethylquercetin crystallised from MeOH as pale yellow needles, $C_{19}H_{18}O_7$, m.p. 158° (Lit.¹⁰ m.p. 159-60°). Found: C, 63.53; H, 4.89. $C_{19}H_{18}O_7$ requires C, 63.68; H, 5.06%. MS: m/e 358 (M^+), 344, 343, 329, 313, 301. It gave colourless crystals of monoacetate, $C_{21}H_{20}O_8$, m.p. 168-69°; 1H nmr (90 MHz): δ 2.46 (3H, *s*, -OAc), 3.80, 3.91, 3.98 (3H, 3H and 6H, *s* each, 4-OMe), 6.62 and 6.83 (1H, *d* each, $J=2.5$ Hz, C-6 and C-8 H), 7.00 (1H, *d*, $J=9$ Hz, C-5' H), 7.67 (1H, *d*, $J=2$ Hz, C-2' H), 7.72 (1H, *dd*, $J_1=9$ Hz, $J_2=2$ Hz, C-6' H). Found: C, 62.99; H, 4.83. $C_{21}H_{20}O_8$ requires C, 62.99; H, 5.04%.

Methylation of quercetin with Me_2SO_4 in presence of NaOAc to 7,4'-dimethylquercetin (3): Methylation of quercetin (1 g) with Me_2SO_4 in dry acetone in presence of NaOAc (instead of $NaHCO_3$) gave 7,4'-dimethyl quercetin (0.56 g) as bright yellow needles, $C_{17}H_{14}O_7$, m.p. 230-31° (Lit.¹¹ m.p. 229-30°), λ_{max} (MeOH) 255, 305 sh, 367 nm ($\log \epsilon$, 4.39, 3.93, 4.38); λ_{max} (MeOH/ $NaOAc$) 255, 305 sh, 367 nm; λ_{max} (MeOH/ $NaOAc/H_3BO_3$) 255, 305 sh, 367 nm; ν_{max} (KBr): 3280, 3450, 1655, 1618 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr (90 MHz): δ 3.86 and 3.99 (3H, *s* each, 2-OMe), 6.30 and 6.58 (1H, *d* each, $J=2.5$ Hz, C-6 and C-8 H), 7.05 (1H, *d*, $J=9$ Hz, C-5' H), 7.77

(2H, *m*, C-2' and C-6' H); MS: *m/e* 330 (M⁺), 315, 301, 287, 259, 231, 149, 135. Found: C, 62.11; H, 4.26. C₁₇H₁₄O₇ requires C, 61.81; H, 4.24%.

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Thiocarbamide as Dealkylating Agent : Debenzylation of Certain 2-S-Benzyl- 1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets with Thiocarbamide

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APLICATION of thiocarbamide as debenzylating agent for 1-aryl-S-benzyl isothiocarbamides in acid medium was reported earlier¹. It is of interest to investigate this debenzylation reaction in other S-benzylated thioamido systems like 2-S-benzyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (I). With this end in view, debenzylations of I have been attempted in basic and acidic conditions. No debenzylation is observed in acid medium. However, smooth debenzylation reaction of I is observed in presence of a tertiary base like pyridine. The present note describes these observations.

The debenzylation reaction of 2-S-benzyl-1,5-diphenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (Ia) with thiocarbamide in presence of pyridine in boiling ethanolic medium

affords a product, m.p. 143°. Elimination of hydrogen sulphide is not observed during the reaction. The product is desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. On pyrolysis, it gives a distinct odour of phenyl isothiocyanate. The ir spectrum of the product clearly indicates the presence of $\nu(\text{NH})$ (3300 cm⁻¹), $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ (1210 cm⁻¹) and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ (705 cm⁻¹) bands². No depression in melting point is observed when it is mixed with an authentic sample of 1,5-diphenyl-2,4-dithiobiuret (IIa)³. On the basis of all these facts, the product with m.p. 143° has been assigned structure IIa. In this reaction, S-benzyl isothiocarbamide (III) has been isolated as its picrate derivative, m.p. 181°.

Other 2-S-benzyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (Ib and Ic) also get debenzylated into the related 1,5-diaryl-2,4-dithiobiurets (IIb and IIc) under analogous reaction conditions.

where R = (a) phenyl, (b) *p*-chlorophenyl and (c) *m*-chlorophenyl and R' = phenyl.

Experimental

The required 2-S-benzyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (I) have been prepared by the interaction of 1-aryl-S-benzyl isothiocarbamides⁴ and aryl isothiocyanates by a known procedure⁵ (Ib, m.p. 120° and Ic, m.p. 102° have been prepared for the first time).

Debenzylation of 2-S-benzyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (I); Formation of 1,5-diaryl-2,4-dithiobiurets (II): Details of a typical experiment (where aryl = phenyl) are as follows:

2-S-benzyl-1,5-diphenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (Ia, 2g) is suspended in ethanol (20 ml) and thiocarbamide (0.4 g) and pyridine (1 ml) are added to this. The reaction mixture is refluxed for 3 hr. Neither hydrogen sulphide nor benzyl mercaptan is eliminated. The reaction mixture is then cooled and acidified with dilute aqueous hydrochloric acid when an oily mass is obtained. The clear supernatant liquid is decanted off and to this is added an aqueous solution of picric acid when a yellow product is obtained. This is filtered and crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 181°. It is identified as the picrate of S-benzyl isothiocarbamide (III).

The oily mass is washed thoroughly with water and then triturated several times with petroleum ether followed by ethanol when a yellow solid